

3 Application and Testing of the FDII Tool

In the context of power systems, erroneous measurements can be divided into two categories: false data and bad data. False data refers to intentionally manipulated or injected measurements designed to mislead the situational awareness of the system operator regarding the state of the monitored power system. In contrast, bad data refer to unintentionally inaccurate or faulty measurements that arise from sensor malfunctions, communication noise, calibration errors, or other random disturbances during data acquisition. These measurements deviate from their true values due to technical or operational issues rather than deliberate manipulation. The presence of both types of erroneous measurements can be detected by applying SE techniques and advanced FDII frameworks.

In this chapter, the FDII tool developed for energy communities within the framework of the COCOON project is applied to the measurement dataset of the HEDNO pilot distribution system (DS). The scope of this test is multifold:

- To validate the performance of the FDII tool under real-field measurements, thereby increasing its technology readiness level.
- To improve the situational awareness of HEDNO for its pilot DS by relying on refined, estimated states rather than raw measurements.
- To create a dataset of estimated states that can be used for the derivation of pseudomeasurements. To elaborate, pseudomeasurements are synthetic measurements used when the number of actual measurements is insufficient to maintain the observability of the monitored DS. Pseudomeasurements can be derived by applying forecasting techniques on historical data; thus, a more refined dataset of estimated states allows for the derivation of more accurate pseudomeasurements compared to the raw measurement dataset.
- To investigate the presence of erroneous measurements, primarily bad data, in the HEDNO measurement dataset. Specifically, applying the FDII tool serves as a quality check on both the metering infrastructure of HEDNO and the consistency between the acquired measurements and the utilised DS models.

3.1 Overview of the FDII Tool

The FDII solution developed for energy communities within the framework of the COCOON project has been presented and validated in detail in D2.2: *Report on the Refinement of the Generic Power Grid State Estimation for PV plants and Energy Communities* [5]. As illustrated in Figure 3.1, the FDII tool comprises four main components: the state estimation (SE), the measurement-based plausibility analysis (MbPA), the false data detection (FDD), and the false data injection response (FDIR), the structure and functionality of which are described in the subsections that follow.

3.1.1 State Estimation

The SE formulation of the FDII instantiation for energy communities is described by the following weighted least squares (WLS) optimization problem:

$$\min \sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}_P} \frac{(P_i - \hat{P}_i)^2}{\sigma_{P_i}^2} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}_Q} \frac{(Q_i - \hat{Q}_i)^2}{\sigma_{Q_i}^2} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}_V} \frac{(V_i - \hat{V}_i)^2}{\sigma_{V_i}^2} + \sum_{i \in \mathcal{M}_I} \frac{(I_i - \hat{I}_i)^2}{\sigma_{I_i}^2} \quad (3.1)$$

subject to:

$$I_{x,i} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (G_{ij} \cdot V_{x,j} - B_{ij} \cdot V_{y,j}), \quad i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (3.2)$$

$$I_{y,i} = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}} (G_{ij} \cdot V_{y,j} + B_{ij} \cdot V_{x,j}), \quad i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (3.3)$$

$$P_i = V_{x,i} \cdot I_{x,i} + V_{y,i} \cdot I_{y,i}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (3.4)$$

$$Q_i = -V_{x,i} \cdot I_{y,i} + V_{y,i} \cdot I_{x,i}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (3.5)$$

$$V_i = \sqrt{V_{x,i}^2 + V_{y,i}^2}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (3.6)$$

$$I_i = \sqrt{I_{x,i}^2 + I_{y,i}^2}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}. \quad (3.7)$$

$$V_{y,i} = 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}_s. \quad (3.8)$$

$$P_i = Q_i = 0, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{zero}}. \quad (3.9)$$

Figure 3.1: Algorithmic implementation of the COCOON generic FDII tool.

To elaborate, the SE considers an active DS of $N + 1$ buses, comprising the set \mathcal{N} , with subsets $\mathcal{M}_P, \mathcal{M}_Q, \mathcal{M}_V$, and \mathcal{M}_I representing the buses with active power, reactive power, voltage magnitude, and current magnitude measurements, respectively. The total measurement set is denoted as $\mathcal{M} = \mathcal{M}_P \cup \mathcal{M}_Q \cup \mathcal{M}_V \cup \mathcal{M}_I$. Moreover, the subset $\mathcal{N}_{\text{zero}}$ represents the zero-injection buses of the system. The singleton set \mathcal{N}_s represents the slack bus of the DS. Variables P_i, Q_i, V_i , and I_i denote the estimated values of active power injection, reactive power injection, voltage magnitude, and current magnitude at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}$, respectively, while parameters $\hat{P}_i, \hat{Q}_i, \hat{V}_i$, and \hat{I}_i denote the corresponding measured values, if available. The measurements are assumed to be affected by additive errors of zero mean value and variance $\sigma_{P_i}^2, \sigma_{Q_i}^2, \sigma_{V_i}^2$, and $\sigma_{I_i}^2$, respectively. Eq. (3.1) is the WLS objective function, while (3.2)-(3.7) represent the non-linear power flow equations in rectangular form. To elaborate, $V_{x,i}$ and $V_{y,i}$ are the real and imaginary parts of the voltage phasor, respectively, while $I_{x,i}$ and $I_{y,i}$ are the real and imaginary parts of the current phasor, respectively. Moreover, G_{ij} and B_{ij} are the real and imaginary parts of the DS admittance matrix, respectively. Eq. (3.8) equivalently sets the phase angle of the slack bus as the angle reference, ensuring that the SE formulation is not underdetermined. Finally, eq. (3.9) leverages the knowledge regarding the zero-injection buses of the DS.

As observed from (3.1)-(3.9), a single-phase SE formulation is proposed in the COCOON solution, since the DS under study operates at the MV level and hosts only three-phase PV plants (Section 3.2.1). Therefore, there are no sources of phase unbalance in the DS. Consequently, the voltage and current unbalance are expected to be negligible under normal operating conditions, allowing the use of a single-phase SE formulation. In turn, the single-phase formulation requires substantially fewer decision variables and thus exhibits higher computational efficiency compared to the three-phase formulation.

3.1.2 Measurement-based Plausibility Analysis

In addition to the SE, a fundamental MbPA module is incorporated into the FDII tool for energy communities. Specifically, the MbPA module applies to the PV buses of the DS—represented by the set \mathcal{N}_{PV} —and verifies whether the rational conditions of (3.10) are satisfied.

$$\hat{P}_i \leq P_{r,i}, \quad \hat{Q}_i \leq P_{r,i}, \quad \sqrt{\hat{P}_i^2 + \hat{Q}_i^2} \leq P_{r,i}, \quad i \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{PV}} \quad (3.10)$$

In (3.10), $P_{r,i}$ denotes the installed capacity of the PV plant at bus $i \in \mathcal{N}_{\text{PV}}$. This simple check can immediately detect erroneous data related to active and reactive power injections at PV buses. Moreover, as illustrated in Figure 3.1, the MbPA module is activated before the SE. Therefore, by acting as a preliminary sanity check that detects obvious erroneous data, the MbPA module enables the SE to provide more reliable results while also reducing its computational burden and execution time.

3.1.3 False Data Detection and False Data Injection Response

In the framework of the FDII instantiation for energy communities, the FDD and FDIR functionalities are implemented by applying the largest normalised residual (LNR) test. More specifically, the LNR test is applied iteratively, as detailed in [6] and presented in Algorithm 3.1, to detect and remove erroneous data from the measurement dataset. As explained in Algorithm 3.1, the LNR test identifies the measurement corresponding to the LNR, that is, the measurement exhibiting the largest normalised deviation from its estimated value. This measurement is considered the most likely to be erroneous. If the LNR is higher than a predefined threshold c , the corresponding measurement is deemed erroneous and removed from the dataset. The procedure is repeated until the LNR falls below c , indicating that all erroneous data have been removed. It is noted that, in Step 3 of Algorithm 3.1, \mathbf{R} is the diagonal measurement covariance matrix. The dimensions of matrix \mathbf{R} are $m \times m$, where m denotes the total number of measurements involved in the SE, including both the actual, meter-derived measurements of set \mathcal{M} and the virtual measurements representing the knowledge of active and reactive power injection at the zero-injection buses.

Table 3.1: Line Characteristics

Lines	R (Ω)	X (Ω)
1-2	2.811	3.116
2-3	0.105	0.073
2-5	0.834	1.063
5-6	0.335	0.231
5-17	0.142	0.220
6-7	0.009	0.006
6-9	0.258	0.178
9-10	0.942	0.649
9-12	0.403	0.278
12-13	0.121	0.083
12-15	0.066	0.045
17-18	0.050	0.035
17-20	0.168	0.261
20-21	0.323	0.223
20-26	0.852	1.323
21-22	0.143	0.098
21-24	0.468	0.322
26-27	0.067	0.046
26-29	0.010	0.016
29-30	0.007	0.005
29-32	0.032	0.049
32-33	0.162	0.112
32-35	0.117	0.181
35-36	0.014	0.010
35-38	0.035	0.054
38-39	0.009	0.006
38-41	0.026	0.041
41-42	0.004	0.003
41-44	0.015	0.024
44-45	0.019	0.029
44-47	0.007	0.005

Table 3.2: Transformer Characteristics

Transformer	x_k (%)	r_k (%)	S_r (MVA)
0-1	15.7	0.14	20
3-4, 10-11, 15-16, 18-19, 24-25, 22-23, 33-34,36-37	5.92	1	1
47-48, 45-46	5.92	1	0.8
27-28, 39-40, 42-43	5.87	1.2	0.5
7-8, 13-14, 30-31	5.87	1.2	0.4

Table 3.3: PV Installed Capacity

Bus index in Figure 3.2	$P_{r,i}$ (kWp)
8	359.34
31	395.56
14	399.52
40, 43	498.96
28	499.79
48	730.75
46	799.74
4	869.13
34	932.99
16, 24	999.00
37	999.35
23	999.50
19	999.75
11	999.96

of the FDII application. More specifically, in Figure 3.3, each pair consisting of a PV plant and its step-up transformer has been replaced by an equivalent PV plant at the MV level, to which the acquired measurements correspond. Moreover, it is noted that all MV buses of Figure 3.2 have been preserved in Figure 3.3, and thus their indexing remains unaltered. The equivalent MV PV buses, indicated in yellow in Figure 3.3, form the set \mathcal{N}_{PV} . The unmonitored buses of Figure 3.3 form the set of zero-injection buses \mathcal{N}_{zero} . Bus 1 forms the singleton set \mathcal{N}_s of the slack bus.

3.2.2 Measurement dataset

The installed smart meters are Itron SL7000 IEC7 devices, corresponding to accuracy of Class 0.5S, Class 1, Class 0.5, and Class 0.5S for active power, reactive power, voltage magnitude, and current magnitude, respectively. The standard deviations σ_{P_i} , σ_{Q_i} , σ_{V_i} , and σ_{I_i} are dynamically calculated according to the accuracy classes of the meters and the current magnitudes, based on the relevant standards [7, 8, 9, 10].

The measurement dataset consists of quarter-hourly measurements of active power injection, reactive power injection, per-phase voltage magnitudes, and per-phase current magnitudes for the 17 monitored buses, i.e., the substation (Bus 1) and the equivalent MV PV buses. In order to obtain representative single-phase voltage and current magnitudes, the mean values of the per-phase quantities are used. It should be noted that mean values

Figure 3.3: Equivalent pilot DS for the FDII application.

are recommended as benchmarks in technical standards [11, 12, 13].

The dataset spans an entire observation year, from May 1st, 2024, at 00:00 until April 30th, 2025, at 23:45. Accordingly, for each monitored bus and measured quantity, there are 35040 measurements, with each measurement corresponding to a distinct 15-minute interval within the observation year.

3.3 Results and discussion

The FDII tool is applied to the measurements of each 15-minute interval, yielding a total of 35040 distinct instances. At each instance, the measurements fed as input into the FDII tool are the active power injection, reactive power injection, voltage magnitude, and current magnitude of each monitored bus, resulting in a total of 68 measurements that constitute the measurement set \mathcal{M} . The equivalent pilot DS model of Figure 3.3 is used. The analysis is performed in per unit (p.u.) with base values of 20 kV for voltage, 1 MVA for active and reactive power, and 28.867 A for current.

3.3.1 Measurement availability and system observability

Despite the continuous monitoring of the pilot DS, not all measurements are available for the entirety of the 35040 instances. In several cases, measurements at a monitored bus are unavailable due to communication malfunctions of the meters or disconnection of the corresponding PV plants. Figure 3.4 illustrates the measurement unavailability per bus and per measured quantity, as a percentage of the 35040 instances. As observed, all measurements exhibit significant unavailability, with the lowest percentage reported for the reactive power measurement of Bus 1 (9.5%) and the highest percentage for the active power measurement of Bus 1 (51%). The average unavailability percentages across all monitored buses are 31.9%, 32.6%, 21%, and 18%, for voltage, current, active power, and reactive power measurements, respectively. The average unavailability percentage across all buses and measured quantities is 25.9%. This significant unavailability results in low measurement redundancy for the monitored DS, i.e., in a low ratio between the number of available measurements and the number of state variables.

Despite the reduced measurement redundancy, the observability of the monitored DS is lost in only 162 out of the 35040 instances, as visualised in Figure 3.5a. More specifically, the observability is preserved thanks to the inclusion of current measurements—which are commonly excluded from standard power flow and state estimation analyses—and due to the 32 virtual measurements that correspond to the known zero active power and reactive power injection at the unmonitored buses of set $\mathcal{N}_{\text{zero}}$.

3.3.2 Erroneous measurements

Regarding erroneous measurements, as illustrated in Figure 3.5b, 80% of the examined instances contain measurements that are detected as bad data. To elaborate further, Figure 3.6 visualizes the rate at which each measurement is detected as bad data relative to the total of 35,040 instances. As observed, measurements are not uniformly detected as bad data, with the majority of them exhibiting detection rates lower than 1%. The five measurements most frequently detected as bad data are the voltage measurements at Bus 7, Bus 36, Bus 1, Bus 10, and Bus 3, listed in descending order of detection rate.

Table 3.4: Maximum and Mean Values for Voltage Sensitivity Factors in p.u./p.u.

Sensitivity Factor	Maximum	Mean
$\frac{dV}{dP}$	0.0104	0.0075
$\frac{dV}{dQ}$	0.0148	0.0109

Indicatively, Figure 3.7 presents the measured voltage profiles for all monitored buses on July 24, 2024. To highlight the differences between the measurements that are most frequently detected as bad data and the remaining measurements, the profiles of Bus 7, Bus 36, Bus 1, Bus 10, and Bus 3 are illustrated with dashed lines and are referenced in the legend of the figure. As observed, the profiles of Bus 7, Bus 36, Bus 1, Bus 10, and Bus 3—i.e., those corresponding to the measurements that are most frequently detected as bad data—are consistently lower than those of the remaining buses throughout the day. More specifically, the voltage of Bus 3 ranges between 0.7 p.u. and 0.8 p.u., an unrealistically low range of values. Similarly, the voltages of Bus 1, Bus 3, Bus 10, and Bus 36, although higher than that of Bus 3, remain visibly lower than the profiles of the other buses. The inset in Figure 3.7 enables a closer examination of the profiles, showing that, for all buses except Bus 1, Bus 3, Bus 10, and Bus 36, the voltage profiles remain very similar throughout the 24-hour window of the day.

This similarity among voltage profiles is attributed to the stiffness of the pilot DS, which is quantified by the $\frac{dV}{dP}$ and $\frac{dV}{dQ}$ voltage sensitivity factors. The maximum and mean values of these sensitivity factors across all monitored buses are listed in Table 3.4. As observed, the sensitivity factors are quite low, which justifies the low voltage variability and, in turn, the similarity of voltage profiles across DS buses. In addition, the low variability of voltage can be further explained by the operating conditions of the DS. More specifically, as observed in Table 3.4, the $\frac{dV}{dQ}$ factors are generally more than 40% higher than the $\frac{dV}{dP}$ factors, rendering voltages more sensitive to reactive power variations. Nevertheless, the PV plants are set to operate with low reactive power exchanges, thereby resulting in stiff voltages and similar profiles.

For a better comparison, Figure 3.8a presents the estimated voltage profiles for all monitored buses on July 24, 2024. As observed, after leveraging the knowledge of the DS topology and parameters, the FDII tool estimates refined voltage profiles that exhibit more realistic time evolutions. More specifically, the obviously erroneous measurements of Bus 3 have been rectified, as well as the consistently lower profiles for Bus 10 and Bus 36. The differences between the originally measured and the refined estimated profiles for Bus 1, Bus 3, Bus 7, Bus 10, and Bus 36 are visualized in Figure 3.8b. It is demonstrated that the voltage profiles for Bus 1, Bus 7, and Bus 10 have been estimated to be higher than their corresponding measurements. Regarding Bus 1, as observed in the inset of Figure 3.8b, the measured and the estimated profiles are similar. Specifically, since Bus 1 is located at the beginning of the feeder and due to the high impedance of line 1-2 (Table 3.1), the lower voltage values compared to the other profiles are justified by the estimation. Nevertheless, the differences between the profiles during the 00:00–06:00 and 19:45–23:45 intervals still indicate that the voltage measurements of Bus 1 are classified as bad data.

To better visualize the detection of erroneous measurements as bad data by the FDII tool, Figure 3.9 illustrates the measurement and estimate profiles across all monitored buses and for all measured quantities, on July 24, 2024, at 12:45. As observed, at this time interval, there are four instances of bad data in the voltage measurements—at Bus 3, Bus 7, Bus 10, and Bus 36—one instance of bad data in the current and active power measurements at Bus 1, and one instance of bad data in the reactive power measurements at Bus 3.

3.3.3 Calculation of Losses

As observed in Figure 3.6c and exemplified by the case of Figure 3.9c, the active power measurement that is most frequently detected as erroneous is that of Bus 1. In contrast, the active power measurements at the PV buses are very rarely detected as bad data. This discrepancy between the measured and estimated active power value at Bus 1 results in differences in the calculation of the active power and energy losses in the DS.

To showcase these differences, Figure 3.10 presents the time evolution of active power losses in the pilot DS on July 24, 2024, both as measured by the installed smart meters and as estimated by the FDII tool. The losses are expressed as a percentage of the aggregate PV installed capacity. As observed, the measurements significantly underestimate the losses during the time interval of high PV generation. Furthermore, in contrast to the estimated profile, which follows the typical bell-shaped curve of PV generation on a sunny day, the measured profile is irregular, exhibiting both spikes and instances of almost zero losses.

In total, the cumulative energy losses for the entire observation year are illustrated in Figure 3.11. As shown, the yearly energy losses are estimated at 595.02 MWh, that is, which is 89.3% higher than the measured value of 314.25 MWh.

3.3.4 Conclusion

To summarize, the results of Section 3.3:

- Validate the FDII tool developed within the framework of the COCOON solution using real-field data.
- Pave the way for the further digitalisation of DSs in Greece. Specifically, the FDII tool enhances HEDNO's situational awareness and monitoring capability by providing refined insights into power losses and highlighting the need to upgrade the metering infrastructure.

Overall, the FDII tool ensures well-monitored and cyber-secure DSs and energy communities, enabling the safe provision of ancillary services, as described in Chapter 4.

Figure 3.4: Measurement unavailability per bus and measured quantity, as a percentage of the 35040 instances.

Figure 3.5: a) Instances with observable and unobservable DS; b) Instances with and without detected bad data.

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Figure 3.6: Detection rate of measurements as bad data per bus and measured quantity, with respect to the total number of instances.

Figure 3.7: Measured voltage profiles at all monitored buses on July 24, 2024.

Figure 3.8: a) Estimated voltage profiles at all monitored buses; (b) Measured and estimated voltage profiles at Bus 1, Bus 3, Bus 7, Bus 10, and Bus 36, on July 24, 2024.

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Figure 3.9: Measured and estimated profiles on July 24, 2024, at 12:45. The insets in subplots (b), (c), and (d) depict the current, active power, and reactive power at Bus 0 separately, as these quantities are considerably larger than those at other buses.

Figure 3.10: Measured and estimated active power losses on July 24, 2024.

Figure 3.11: Cumulative energy losses.

4 Ancillary Services

4.1 Ancillary Services Overview

In this section, the provision of voltage-related and frequency-related ancillary services (AS) by the pilot DS is described and demonstrated. To elaborate, the PV plants of the I&K energy community are controlled to perform voltage regulation and to enable the pilot DS to operate as a frequency containment reserve (FCR) for the upstream electric power and energy system (EPES). More specifically, the voltage regulation is performed in a decentralized manner by controlling the PV plants in voltage-reactive power mode through a $Q(V)$ droop curve, as well as in active power-reactive power mode through a $Q(P)$ droop curve, in accordance with the IEEE 1547-2018 Standard [14]. The operation as an FCR is achieved by implementing a $P(f)$ droop curve in compliance with the Network Code on Requirements for Generators (RfG) [15].

4.1.1 Voltage-Related Ancillary Services

In the IEEE 1547 Standard [14], Distributed Energy Resources (DERs) are classified into Category A and Category B with respect to voltage regulation. Category B corresponds to larger, more critical DERs and stipulates stricter requirements. For this reason, the analysis and implementation of the voltage-related AS within the framework of the COCOON project focus on the requirements of Category B.

Figure 4.1: $Q(V)$ droop based on the IEEE 1547 Standard - Category B DERs.

Under the voltage-reactive power control mode, DERs shall regulate their reactive power output as a function of voltage, following a predefined piecewise-linear $Q(V)$ (voltage-reactive power) characteristic. Unless otherwise specified by the corresponding DSO, the $Q(V)$ characteristic shall be configured according to the default parameter values listed in Table 4.1. If specified by the DSO, the characteristic shall instead be configured using values within the optional allowable range of Table 4.1. The $Q(V)$ characteristic may be adjusted locally and/or remotely based on the requirements set by the DSO. An example of a $Q(V)$ characteristic under the default settings is demonstrated in Figure 4.1.

Furthermore, DERs shall be capable of autonomously adjusting the reference voltage V_{ref} , setting it equal to the low-pass-filtered locally measured voltage. The time constant of the low pass filter applied to the locally measured voltage shall be adjustable and within the range of 300 seconds to 5000 seconds. The $Q(V)$ characteristic shall also be adjusted autonomously, following the adjustment of V_{ref} . Nevertheless, the autonomous adjustment of V_{ref} requires the approval of the DSO, who also determines the implementation of the autonomous V_{ref} adjustability and the associated time constant.

Under the active power-reactive power control mode, DERs shall regulate their reactive power output as a function of the active power output, following a predefined piecewise-linear $Q(P)$ characteristic, without any intentional time delay. Unless otherwise specified by the corresponding DSO, the $Q(P)$ characteristic shall be configured according to the default parameter values listed in Table 4.2. If specified by the DSO, the

Table 4.1: Voltage-reactive power settings for normal operating performance (Category B DERs)

Parameter	Default settings	Allowable range	
		Minimum	Maximum
V_{ref}	V_n	$0.95 V_n$	$1.05 V_n$
V_1	$V_{\text{ref}} - 0.08 V_n$	$V_{\text{ref}} - 0.18 V_n$	$V_2 - 0.02 V_n$
V_2	$V_{\text{ref}} - 0.02 V_n$	$V_{\text{ref}} - 0.03 V_n$	V_{ref}
V_3	$V_{\text{ref}} + 0.02 V_n$	V_{ref}	$V_{\text{ref}} + 0.03 V_n$
V_4	$V_{\text{ref}} + 0.08 V_n$	$V_3 + 0.02 V_n$	$V_{\text{ref}} + 0.18 V_n$
Q_1 (at V_1)	$+0.44 S_{\text{rated}}$	0	Q_{rated}
Q_2 (at V_2)	0	$-Q_{\text{rated}}$	Q_{rated}
Q_3 (at V_3)	0	$-Q_{\text{rated}}$	Q_{rated}
Q_4 (at V_4)	$-0.44 S_{\text{rated}}$	$-Q_{\text{rated}}$	0
Open-loop response time	5 s	1 s	90 s

Notes. V_n : nominal system voltage. S_{rated} : nameplate apparent power rating of the DER. Q_{rated} : nameplate reactive power capability of the DER. Positive and negative reactive power indicate generation and absorption, respectively.

Figure 4.2: $Q(P)$ droop based on the IEEE 1547 Standard - Category B DERs.

characteristic shall instead be configured using values within the optional allowable range of Table 4.2. The $Q(P)$ characteristic may be adjusted locally and/or remotely based on the requirements set by the DSO. In all cases, the response time should not exceed 10 seconds. The generic form of the $Q(P)$ characteristics is presented in Figure 4.2. It is noted that the portion of Figure 4.2 corresponding to negative active power values, along with the associated Table 4.2 requirements, applies only to DERs that are capable of absorbing active power; hence, the I&K PV plants are excluded.

4.1.2 Frequency-Related Ancillary Services

The COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) 2016/631 on RfG establishes harmonized rules for the connection of power-generating modules (PGMs) to the European EPES [15]. Among its core provisions are requirements for frequency stability, implemented through the $P(f)$ droop characteristic, whereby active power output varies proportionally with system frequency deviations. This control scheme ensures that all generators—from small distributed PV inverters to large-scale power plants—contribute as FCRs to the overall system resilience. Specifically, RfG defines four types of PGMs: Type A, Type B, Type C, and Type D. The categorization is based on rated power and connection voltage, with thresholds adapted to each synchronous area. In Continental Europe, Type A modules cover the smallest units, from 0.8 kW up to below 1 MW; Type B includes modules

Table 4.2: Active power–reactive power settings for normal operating performance (Category B DERs)

Parameter	Default settings	Allowable range	
		Minimum	Maximum
P_3	P_{rated}	$P_2 + 0.1 P_{\text{rated}}$	P_{rated}
P_2	$0.5 P_{\text{rated}}$	$0.4 P_{\text{rated}}$	$0.8 P_{\text{rated}}$
P_1	$\max\{0.2 P_{\text{rated}}, P_{\text{min}}\}$	P_{min}	$P_2 - 0.1 P_{\text{rated}}$
P'_1	$\min\{0.2 P'_{\text{rated}}, P'_{\text{min}}\}$	$P'_2 - 0.1 P'_{\text{rated}}$	P'_{min}
P'_2	$0.5 P'_{\text{rated}}$	$0.8 P'_{\text{rated}}$	$0.4 P'_{\text{rated}}$
P'_3	P'_{rated}	P'_{rated}	$P'_2 + 0.1 P'_{\text{rated}}$
Q_3	$-0.44 S_{\text{rated}}$	$-Q_{\text{rated}}$	Q_{rated}
Q_2	0	$-Q_{\text{rated}}$	Q_{rated}
Q_1	0	$-Q_{\text{rated}}$	Q_{rated}
Q'_1	0	$-Q_{\text{rated}}$	Q_{rated}
Q'_2	0	$-Q_{\text{rated}}$	Q_{rated}
Q'_3	$+0.44 S_{\text{rated}}$	$-Q_{\text{rated}}$	Q_{rated}

Notes. P_{rated} : nameplate active power rating of the DER. P'_{rated} : maximum, in amplitude, active power that the DER can absorb. P_{min} : minimum active power output of the DER. P'_{min} : minimum, in amplitude, active power that the DER can absorb.

from 1 MW up to below 50 MW; Type C applies to units above 50 MW but below 75 MW, while Type D refers to the largest units, typically above 75 MW or connected at 110 kV or higher.

The operation of PGMs with respect to frequency stability is defined through two main modes: the Limited Frequency Sensitive Mode (LFSM) and the Frequency Sensitive Mode (FSM). The LFSM requires the PGM to adjust its active power proportionally, but only when frequency deviates beyond a defined deadband. The LFSM is further classified as LFSM-O and LFSM-U, depending on whether the frequency deviations are overfrequencies or underfrequencies, respectively. In contrast, the FSM requires an almost continuous proportional response of active power to frequency deviations across a defined frequency range, rendering it a more stringent operating mode that ensures full participation of the PGM as an FCR. More specifically, the deadband for the FSM is restricted to 10-30 mHz, while the deadbands for the LFSM-O and LFSM-U range between 200-500 mHz.

According to the RfG, Type A modules are only obliged to operate under LFSM-O. This means they must reduce their active power output whenever system frequency exceeds a threshold between 50.2 Hz and 50.5 Hz, following a droop in the range of 2–12%. Type B modules are also required to operate under LFSM-O, and may be also required to operate under LFSM-U, i.e. to increase their active power during underfrequency conditions. Type A and Type B PGMs are not required to operate under FSM. In contrast, Type C and Type D PGMs are required to operate under the FSM. Therefore, their active power output must continuously follow frequency deviations with the associated operating bands, deadbands, droop settings, and response times being defined in the RfG. The requirements for Type D modules are aligned with those for Type C but include stricter compliance verification and monitoring obligations, reflecting their higher impact of these PGMs on system stability. Overall, the characteristics of the different operating modes and their applicable PGMs are summarized in Table 4.3.

Since the PV plants of the I&K energy community have installed capacities ranging from 0.36 MWp to 1 MWp, they fall under the Type A category. Therefore, they should operate with LFSM-O and a deadband. A generic

Table 4.3: Comparison of different $P(f)$ droop requirements per type of PGM, according to RfG 631/2016, [15]

Module Type	LFSM-O	LFSM-U	FSM
Type A	Mandatory – Active power reduction when $f > 50.2\text{--}50.5$ Hz. Droop: 2–12%. Must stay connected between 47.5–51.5 Hz.	Not required.	Not required.
Type B	Mandatory – Same as Type A: reduction above 50.2–50.5 Hz with droop 2–12%.	Optional (TSO decision) – May be required to increase active power when $f < 49.5\text{--}49.8$ Hz. Droop: 2–12%.	Not required.
Type C	Mandatory – Reduction when $f > 50.2\text{--}50.5$ Hz. Droop: 2–12%.	Mandatory – Increase active power when $f < 49.5\text{--}49.8$ Hz. Droop: 2–12%.	Mandatory – Continuous proportional response within 49.5–50.5 Hz, configurable deadband (10–30 mHz), droop 2–12%.
Type D	Mandatory – Same as Type C.	Mandatory – Same as Type C.	Mandatory – Same as Type C, but with stricter validation, testing, and monitoring requirements.

Figure 4.3: (Left) $P(f)$ droop based on the RfG; (Right) proposed $Q(f)$ droop. DB stands for deadband.

$P(f)$ droop curve with deadband is presented in Figure 4.3-(Left). In addition, for preliminary tests, the PV plants of the energy community were set to operate under a $Q(f)$ droop curve, as shown in Figure 4.3-(Right). More specifically, although not a standard AS, the $Q(f)$ droop control was selected and implemented as a preliminary step, in order to test the effectiveness and the correct mathematical modeling of the control curve, without causing unnecessary active power curtailments and, consequently, income losses for the plant owners.

4.2 Implementation and testing of AS in the real pilot setup

This section analyzes the implementation and testing of the AS described in Section 4.1. For voltage-related AS, the $Q(V)$ and $Q(P)$ droop control schemes are tested, while for frequency-related AS, the $Q(f)$ and $P(f)$ droop control schemes are tested. All droop control schemes are implemented through Python scripts. Specifically, the scripts receive voltage, active power, and frequency measurements from the I&K PV plants, and calculate the corresponding reactive power—for the $Q(V)$, $Q(P)$, and $Q(f)$ droop control schemes—and active power—for the $P(f)$ droop control scheme—operating points for the provision of the AS. Subsequently, these operating points are sent as setpoints to the PV plants. In the conducted tests, measurements were received every 5 seconds, and setpoints were sent every 30 seconds; however, these time intervals are parameterized in the Python scripts and can be easily adjusted. The Python scripts are provided in Zenodo, [16]. It is noted that measurements are received from the low-voltage points of interconnection of the I&K PV plants, indicated in Figure 3.2 as AS-monitored buses.

4.2.1 Assumptions

This subsection discusses the assumptions for the implementation of the AS.

4.2.1.1 Voltage-related AS

Regarding the voltage-related AS, the reactive power setpoints for the implementation of the $Q(V)$ and $Q(P)$ droops are calculated based on the average RMS voltage or three-phase active power measured values, respectively. As discussed in detail in Section 4.2.2, the number of measurements included in the averaging process is a configurable parameter in the Python implementation scripts.

4.2.1.2 Frequency-related AS

Regarding the frequency-related AS, instead of measuring the actual system frequency, an overfrequency event was emulated for the following reason: in the EPES of Continental Europe, frequency typically exhibits only small deviations, and frequency events are rare; therefore, FCRs are not frequently activated. The emulated frequency event was derived from the frequency disturbance that occurred on January 8, 2021. During this event, the Continental Europe synchronous area split into two regions at 14:04 CET due to several transmission system element outages, which caused a power deficit and frequency drop in the North-West, and a power surplus and frequency increase in the South-East. This separation resulted from the simultaneous and cascading tripping of multiple transmission system elements. The split led to a 6.3 GW power deficit in the North-West area and a 6.3 GW surplus in the South-East. As observed in Figure 4.4, the event was resolved by 15:08 CET through coordinated actions by transmission system operators and the activation of countermeasures, including the disconnection of 1.7 GW from industrial and commercial consumers contracted to provide load shedding services as interruptible loads [17].

Regarding the pilot implementation, to emulate a fictional frequency event for the purpose of testing the frequency-related AS schemes, a representative frequency signal was devised based on the system split event. More specifically, the system frequency trajectory during the disturbance—i.e., from 14:04 CET to 14:05:10 CET—was isolated, as shown in the inset of Figure 4.5-(Left), where the frequency exhibits a maximum deviation before briefly returning to its nominal value (50 Hz). To accommodate the communication constraints of the SDG—which transmits data at 5-second intervals—the signal was time-stretched to a total duration of approximately 70 minutes. The resulting waveform, illustrated in Figure 4.5-(Right), was used as the emulated frequency profile in the pilot tests.

The test was designed as such to reach a maximum deviation and briefly return to its nominal value (50 Hz). Subsequently, this signal was extended in time to last approximately 70 minutes, yielding the emulated frequency signal used for the pilots tests, as illustrated in Figure 4.5-(Right). The total duration of approximately 70 minutes was chosen due to the sampling constraints of the SDG, which is able to send data points every 5 seconds and cannot transmit at a higher rate.

Figure 4.4: Frequency event on January 8, 2021, as reported by ENTSO-E [17]: (Upper left) Frequency in Continental Europe immediately after the disturbance and during resynchronization; (Upper right) Frequency in Continental Europe over the full duration of the event; (Bottom) Separation of the Continental Europe synchronous area.

4.2.2 Description of Implementation

In this subsection, the implementation procedure is described and depicted in algorithmic form.

For the voltage-related AS, the Python script `Voltage_related_AS_vFinal_all_pvs` was developed. For the frequency-related AS, the scripts `Frequency_related_AS_Q-f_vFinal` and `Frequency_related_AS_P-f_vFinal` were developed for the $Q(f)$ and $P(f)$ droop control implementation, respectively. The

Figure 4.5: (Left) Reference frequency event, with the inset illustrating the frequency disturbance (time in UTC); (Right) Emulated frequency signal used for testing purposes.

algorithmic structures for the voltage-related and the frequency-related AS are presented in Figure 4.6 and in Figure 4.7, respectively.

In general, the algorithms for both types of AS involve four stages, which are indicated by different colors in Figure 4.6 and Figure 4.7:

1. **The initialization stage**, in which input parameters are acquired and control modes are defined by the user;
2. **The measurement acquisition stage**, in which measurements are retrieved from the SQL database of the SDG and are aggregated in a common format;
3. **The control stage**, in which the droop control schemes are selected and implemented;
4. **The output stage**, in which all output data are collected at each time step as an updated row or as distinct columns in respective CSV files. In this final stage, the setpoints are sent from the SDG to the PV plants.

To elaborate, the initialization stage involves reading the file named `IEC104_Tags.xlsx`, so as to construct an internal mapping dictionary that links each PV unit or head of the feeder (Bus 1 of Figure 3.2) to its corresponding measurement and control parameters. This mapping associates key identifiers—such as the IEC 104 information address, measured or control variable, and SDG tag name—with each electrical quantity. Using this reference, the system establishes communication pathways to read real-time telemetry data from field devices and to issue setpoint or control commands. The resulting mapping framework ensures consistent data acquisition, control execution, and seamless integration of all needed elements within the supervisory control and monitoring architecture. It should be noted that the measurements of Bus 1 are referred to as TRIAD measurements, due to the same-name measuring device that is connected at the head of the feeder, as discussed in Chapter 2. Furthermore, during this stage, the algorithm imports the installed capacities of the energy community PVs. In addition, the user is prompted to select control modes, which are discussed in detail in the following paragraphs.

In the measurement acquisition stage, the function `measurements_acquisition` is used to connect with the SQL database of the SDG and import the measurements from the SQL database. Afterwards, in the main code, CSV files are created to log the measurements and the setpoints, along with their timestamps. It is noted that the measurements are aggregated and averaged every $\Delta\tau_m$, which is a configurable time interval defined in the script, while the control setpoints are sent every $\Delta\tau_s$, which is an integer k multiple of $\Delta\tau_m$ ($\Delta\tau_s = k \cdot \Delta\tau_m$). Therefore, each setpoint is calculated with respect to the average of k measurements.

The third stage, i.e., the control stage, varies depending on the AS, as described in detail in the following

paragraphs. As a general note for this stage, for the SDG, it is required to write the calculated setpoints in the SQL database, which further sends them to the PV plants; this is implemented in the function named `control_pv_set_vFinal`.

The output stage involves writing the measurements and setpoints—when sent—together with their respective timestamps, into a new row in the created CSV file.

Furthermore, as mentioned, both the voltage-related and the frequency-related algorithms prompt the user to select control modes, with the selection determining the functions and operations executed in the control stage. Regarding the voltage related AS, the script prompts the user to select between $Q(V)$ (Option 1) or $Q(P)$ (Option 2) control. Then, depending on the choice, the function `RP_choice_control` returns the reactive power setpoint in p.u., based on the average (over k measurements) voltage or active power in p.u., as computed by the respective droop functions `RP_V_control` or `RP_P_control`. These droop functions implement the droop control curves of Figure 4.1 and Figure 4.2, respectively.

Regarding the $P(f)$ control, the script prompts the user through the function `f_P_choice_control` to select between two different implementations of the droop curve shown in Figure 4.3-(Left): either defining the slope of the droop with values between 2%-12% using the function `f_P_control_droop_in`, or defining the headroom p_{min} using the function `f_P_control_HD_in`. The same structure is used for the $Q(f)$, with the main difference being that q_{min} must not be less than $-q_{max}$, as shown in Figure 4.3-(Right). Finally, the user can define the deadband in mHz and the frequency range $df_{range}=f_{max} - f_{min}$ in Hz, as illustrated in Figures 4.3.

4.3 Field Results

In this section the field results are presented and discussed. The five PVs of the I&K energy community are denoted as PV1, PV2, PV3, PV4, PV5, as depicted in Figure 3.2. It is noted that the results presented in p.u. refer to the installed capacity of each PV.

4.3.1 Reactive Power - Frequency

The first AS to be tested was the $Q(f)$ droop control, with the Python script `Frequency_related_AS_Q-f_vFinal` executed on May 20th, 2025. Specifically, the option `f_Q_control_droop_in` was selected, along with a slope of 8%, for the provision of reactive power response based on the variations in the emulated frequency signal of Figure 4.5-(Right). The signal was loaded from the external file `Incident_mock_up.xlsx`. The deadband was set to zero, and the frequency range $df_{range}=f_{max} - f_{min}$ was set to 1 Hz.

The results are presented in Figure 4.8 and Figure 4.9. Only PV1, PV2 and PV5 responded to the $Q(f)$ setpoints, while PV3 and PV4 were affected by communication issues. Figure 4.8 shows a minor lag in response, which in turn reflects a slight delay in the SDG response. Deviations from the reference values are mainly observed during the initial transmission of setpoints. These deviations correspond to the initialization phase of the control process and are attributed to transient phenomena occurring while the SDG communication channel is being established, prior to achieving a stable operational state. Figure 4.9 demonstrates good adherence of PV1, PV2, and PV5 to the imposed droop. Overall, the deviations between measured and reference slopes are mostly small, indicating a successful validation of the $Q(f)$ droop implementation.

4.3.2 Active Power - Frequency

The AS testing was interrupted during summer months due to communication issues with the SDG. After resolving these communication problems, the Python script `Frequency_related_AS_P-f_vFinal` script was executed on September 8, 2025, to test the $P(f)$ droop. Specifically, the option `f_P_control_droop_in` was selected, along with a slope of 2%, for the provision of active power response based on the variations in the emulated frequency signal of Figure 4.5-(Right). The signal was loaded from the external file `Incident_mock_up.xlsx`. The deadband was set to zero, and the frequency range $df_{range}=f_{max} - f_{min}$ was set to 0.8 Hz.

The results are presented in Figure 4.10, Figure 4.11, and Figure 4.12. Only PV1, PV2, PV3, and PV5 responded to the $P(f)$ setpoints, while PV4 was affected by communication issues. To validate the correct implementation of the $P(f)$ droop curve, the active power output of the PVs is measured and compared with the calculated

Figure 4.6: Algorithmic structure for implementing voltage-related AS.

setpoint, as presented in Figure 4.10. The results demonstrate a good agreement between the actual measured active power output of the PVs and the desired setpoints, confirming the correct implementation of the droop curve. The accurate tracking of the PVs to the imposed droop is further confirmed in Figure 4.11. Moreover, it is noted that the steep slope of 2% resulted in PV power curtailment, as the artificial frequency exceeded 50.4 Hz. Finally, Figure 4.12 displays the system-level response at the head of the feeder, including active power, reactive power, and voltage.

The $P(f)$ was further tested on September 9, 2025. Specifically, the Python script `Frequency_related_AS_P-f_vFinal` was executed, selecting the option `f_P_control_droop_in` but a more relaxed slope of 8%. The deadband was set to zero and the frequency range df_{range} to 1 Hz. It should be noted that, in this test, p_{max}

Figure 4.7: Algorithmic structure for implementing frequency-related AS.

in Figure 4.3-(Left) was set to 0.35 p.u., as the test was conducted early in the morning—i.e., during hours of low PV generation—and there is no maximum power point tracking system to help estimate dynamically the available p_{max} . The results are presented in Figure 4.13, Figure 4.14, and Figure 4.15. All PVs responded in this test. Both Figure 4.13 and Figure 4.14 demonstrate that the actual measured active power output of the PVs adheres well to the imposed droop control logic, thereby confirming its effective implementation. Moreover, since no active power curtailment occurred during these tests, the power adjustment is more noticeable.

Figure 4.8: Reactive power and voltage for three PVs of the energy community under the $Q(f)$ characteristic on May 20, 2025: (Left) Per-unit Values; (Right) Physical values. Continuous light green line corresponds to the reactive power measurements, dashed blue line corresponds to the reactive power setpoints and continuous orange line corresponds to average phase voltage measurements.

4.3.3 Reactive Power - Voltage

The $Q(V)$ droop was tested on September 9, 2025, through an almost 24-hour run of the script `Voltage_related_AS_vFinal_all_pvs`. Specifically, Option 1 was selected in the function `RP_choice_control`, activating the function `RP_V_control`. The results are presented in Figure 4.16, Figure 4.17, Figure 4.18, and Figure 4.19. All PVs responded during this test. Figure 4.16 demonstrates the reactive power response of the PVs with respect to variations in the measured voltage, confirming the strong alignment between the measured and the reference $Q(V)$ curves across all PVs. In a similar manner to the frequency-related AS, small discrepancies between measured and reference values are linked to the initialization phase of the control process, i.e., during the setup of the SDG communication channel. The deviations disappear once stable data exchange is established.

The evolution of active and reactive power, as well as of the average phase voltage, during the 24-hour test are presented in Figure 4.17 and Figure 4.18 for PV1 and PV4, respectively. It is noted that these two PVs are the most remote with respect to the head of the feeder. The results demonstrate the excellent decentralized voltage support of the $Q(V)$ droop control schemes, which is sustained over long durations. Finally, Figure 4.19 displays the system-level response at the head of the feeder, including active power, reactive power, and voltage.

4.3.4 Reactive Power - Active Power

The $Q(P)$ droop was tested on September 12, 2025, through an almost 24-hour run of the script `Voltage_related_AS_vFinal_all_pvs`. Specifically, Option 2 was selected in the function `RP_choice_control`, activating the function `RP_P_control`. The results are presented in Figure 4.20, Figure 4.21, Figure 4.22, and Figure 4.23. All PVs responded during this test. Figure 4.20 demonstrates the reactive power response of the PVs with respect to variations in the measured active power, confirming the strong alignment between the measured and the reference $Q(P)$ curves across all PVs. Similarly to $Q(V)$, minor differences between measured and reference values arise during the SDG communication setup phase but vanish once stable data exchange is established.

The evolution of active and reactive power, as well as of the average phase voltage, during the 24-hour test are presented in Figure 4.21 and Figure 4.22 for PV1 and PV4, respectively. It is noted that these two PVs are the most remote with respect to the head of the feeder. The results demonstrate the excellent decentralized voltage support of the $Q(V)$ droop control schemes, which is sustained over long durations. Moreover, it is observed

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Figure 4.9: Comparison of the measured $Q(f)$ characteristic with the setpoint droop for PV1 (first row), PV2 (second row), and PV5 (third row), on May 20, 2025: (Left) Per-unit values; (Right) Physical values.

that the reactive power output—due to its proportionality to active power imposed by the $Q(P)$ droop—exhibits a profile similar to that of the solar generation curves. Finally, Figure 4.23 displays the system-level response at the head of the feeder, including active power, reactive power, and voltage.

4.3.5 General Remarks and Conclusions

Regarding the TRIAD measurements, a general comment concluding this section is that some oscillations appear in the active and reactive power at the head of the feeder (around 50kW and 30kVAR, respectively), which are particularly visible in Figures 4.15, 4.19, 4.23. These oscillations are attributed to the measurement tolerance of the voltage and current transformers. Finally, the results presented in Figures 4.8-4.23 demonstrate the successful field validation of both frequency and voltage AS by energy communities in active DSs.

Figure 4.10: Measurements and setpoints of active power for four PVs of the energy community under the $P(f)$ characteristic with droop slope equal to 2% on September 8, 2025: (Left) Per-unit values; (Right) Physical values.

Figure 4.11: Comparison of the measured $P(f)$ (2%) characteristic with the setpoint droop for PV1 (first row), PV2 (second row), PV3 (third row), and PV5 (fourth row), on September 8, 2025: (Left) Per-unit values; (Right) Physical values.

Figure 4.12: TRIAD measurements from the head of the feeder during the $P(f)$ characteristic test with droop slope equal to 2% on September 8, 2025: (Upper Left) Active Power; (Upper Right) Reactive Power; (Bottom Left) Line-to-line voltages; (Bottom Right) Average line-to-line voltage.

Figure 4.13: Measurements and setpoints of active power for all PVs of the energy community under the $P(f)$ characteristic with droop slope equal to 8% on September 9, 2025: (Left) Per-unit values; (Right) Physical values.

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Figure 4.14: Comparison of the measured $P(f)$ (8%) characteristic with the setpoint droop for PV1 (first row), PV2 (second row), PV3 (third row), PV4 (fourth row), and PV5 (fifth row), on September 9, 2025: (Left) Per-unit values; (Right) Physical values.

Figure 4.15: TRIAD measurements from the head of the feeder during the $P(f)$ characteristic test with droop slope equal to 8% on September 9, 2025: (Upper Left) Active Power; (Upper Right) Reactive Power; (Bottom Left) Line-to-line voltages; (Bottom Right) Average line-to-line voltage.

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Figure 4.16: Comparison of the measured $Q(V)$ characteristic with the setpoint droop for PV1 (first row), PV2 (second row), PV3 (third row), PV4 (fourth row), and PV5 (fifth row), on September 9, 2025: (Left) Per-unit values; (Right) Physical values.

Figure 4.17: PV1 measurements and setpoints (physical values) during the almost 24-hour test with the $Q(V)$ characteristic on September 9-10, 2025. The figures depict the interval from 11:00 to 20:00 on September 9, 2025, during which there was significant reactive power flow: (Upper Left) Active Power; (Upper Right) Reactive Power; (Bottom) Average Phase Voltage.

Figure 4.18: PV4 measurements and setpoints (physical values) during the almost 24-hour test with the $Q(V)$ characteristic on September 9-10, 2025. The figures depict the interval from 11:00 to 20:00 on September 9, 2025, during which there was significant reactive power flow (Upper Left) Active Power; (Upper Right) Reactive Power; (Bottom) Average Phase Voltage.

Figure 4.19: TRIAD measurements from the head of the feeder during the almost 24-hour test of the $Q(V)$ droop, on September 9-10, 2025: (Upper Left) Active Power; (Upper Right) Reactive Power; (Bottom Left) Line-to-line voltages; (Bottom Right) Average line-to-line voltage.

4.3. Field Results

Figure 4.20: Comparison of the measured $Q(P)$ characteristic with the setpoint droop for PV1 (first row), PV2 (second row), PV3 (third row), PV4 (fourth row), and PV5 (fifth row), on September 12, 2025: (Left) Per-unit values; (Right) Physical values.

Figure 4.21: PV1 measurements and setpoints (physical values) during the almost 24-hour test under the $Q(V)$ characteristic on September 12-13, 2025. The figures depict the interval from 07:00 to 17:00 on September 13, 2025, during which there was significant reactive power flow: (Upper Left) Active Power; (Upper Right) Reactive Power; (Bottom) Average Phase Voltage.

Figure 4.22: PV4 measurements and setpoints (physical values) during the almost 24-hour test under the $Q(V)$ characteristic on September 12-13, 2025. The figures depict the interval from 07:00 to 17:00 on September 13, 2025, during which there was significant reactive power flow: (Upper Left) Active Power; (Upper Right) Reactive Power; (Bottom) Average Phase Voltage.

Figure 4.23: TRIAD measurements from the head of the feeder during the almost 24-hour test of the $Q(P)$ droop, on September 12-13, 2025: (Upper Left) Active Power; (Upper Right) Reactive Power; (Bottom Left) Line-to-line voltages; (Bottom Right) Average line-to-line voltage.